

ECONOMIC SCIENCES

DETERMINANTS FOR THE FORMATION OF SOCIO-ECONOMIC COMPONENT OF NATIONAL SECURITY

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Abstract

The article the determinants of the formation of socio-economic security as an integral part of the national security of the state analyzed. The field of analytical support of economic security management acquires new features with the strengthening of the digitalization of the economy and the strengthening of the negative consequences of global economic crises, risks of business environment. The definite sources of socio-economic security as an integral part of the national security of the state are analyzed. A systematic approach to assessing socio-economic security is considered and it is determined that socio-economic security is a state characterized by the protection of the socio-economic system from macro-environment threats, which provides opportunities for self-development, conservation, an appropriate social state and level of life support in conditions of an appropriate level. profitability and consistency and the realization of economic interests. It was determined that along with the development of measures to strengthen economic security as a component of national security at the macro level, economic security management at the level of economic entities plays a significant role.

Keywords: socio-economic security, economic structure, social development, analysis, business entities, control.

At present, the interpretation of national security is considered primarily in the context of ensuring economic independence, social stability, stability of the political system and military-defense ability to protect the territorial integrity of the country. The main determinants of the formation of economic security are its relationship with the external and internal environment of the functioning of the state at the macroeconomic level and economic entities at the microeconomic level, as well as with the level of its protection from market dangers and economic threats. However, consideration of economic security solely from the point of view of protection from threats does not reflect the totality of cause-and-effect relationships and components that are embodied in it as a component of national security.

A preliminary analysis of the theoretical aspects showed that at present there are different approaches to the interpretation of such a definition as "economic security". It is considered as a process of meeting public needs, protecting the national interests of the state, economic stability and stability of the economic system, a state of the national economy in which the state does not lose its sovereignty and protects its economic environment from external threats. That is why we propose to consider economic security in its dialectical relationship with the development of the social system of the state and its balance in the temporary space of economic activity.

The high level of integration of the country's economy into raw materials markets based on price competition, rather than competition between technologies and innovations, poses a significant risk to the stable

operation of the economy [1-3]. The dynamics of the Ukrainian economic structure does not correspond to the general laws of structural changes, which presently occur in the world's developed economies and consist in increasing the share of high-tech processing industry, telecommunications, financial and business services, as well as socially oriented economic activities, and in the advanced development of knowledge-intensive high-tech industries.

Instead, Ukraine has an inefficient economic structure with highly resource-intensive and energy-intensive production, economically backward agribusiness, low level of innovative production, lagging infrastructure development, financial sector non-correlated with the real economy, inefficient operation of the sectors involved in social development [4].

In general, the trends specified are consistent with the global economic structural transformations, are characteristic primarily of emerging economies and step-by-step bring the structure of domestic economy closer to the ratios typical of highly developed countries.

However, the decrease in the role of the real sector economy is to be followed by a significant growth in labor productivity through the introduction of innovative technologies, which is not observed in Ukraine [5]. The growth of domestic economy in the pre-crisis period, determined by the combined action of both internal and external favorable factors, had a restorative nature and was not accompanied by critically needed progressive structural changes and technical progress. The national economy remained poorly diversified and,

therefore, vulnerable to the world market volatility, it was characterized by a low level of innovations and resource efficiency. Thus, the implementation of an export-oriented strategy in the domestic and foreign wholesale markets requires radical changes and the development of an action plan that provides for the expansion of the existing market, innovation or diversification of production [6].

The economic dynamics was determined by the combined effect of both internal and external favorable factors, however, no stable uptrends were formed, but the economic growth was characterized by high volatility of macroeconomic dynamics, not accompanied by systemic reforms, thus exacerbating the existing imbalance. The growing role of the financial sector is not accompanied by an adequate improvement of lending conditions in the real economy and by intensification of investment processes. Each sector of the social sphere has accumulated a number of significant structural problems.

In recent years, Ukraine has been facing increasing social tensions, lowering demographic indices, deterioration of living standards and quality of life, especially in rural areas, together with stagnation in the innovation area, especially in small and medium-sized businesses. It requires closer attention, well-balanced management decisions and management focused on these factors as sources of future comfort of living, new job openings and a quality boost for the economic growth of business entities.

It is this structural transformation of the economy that ensures the adaptation of domestic business to the global operating environment in order to meet social needs and socio-economic growth. Diagnostics of structural transformations of the economy by its main types indicates the presence of significant imbalances, which poses a threat to achieving the goals. Changes in the political, economic and social life of Ukraine in recent years are not only limited to the search for new ways of doing business, but have set a number of tasks to ensure the viability of the country in the new economic conditions [7].

In order to optimize and improve the efficiency of the national economic structure, it is necessary to pursue an active structural policy involving the potential of all state institutions. We can supplement the theoretical understanding of the content of economic security, which is still considered mainly from the standpoint of countering risks and threats and achieving competitive advantages in an unstable environment. The structural policy should be based on a detailed analysis of the impact of basic market and social institutions on the structure of the domestic economy.

The research of risks caused by both excessive and insufficient administrative influence on the activities of transnational companies makes it possible to identify the negative consequences of the processes under consideration both for the country as a whole and for its individual regions and systematize threats to the country in the field of economic security formation in terms of the nature relationships between economic entities and public authorities in the context of globalization processes [8].

In general, economic security can be characterized as a set of conditions necessary to ensure the normal economic development of the country and restore the gap in development compared to European countries during Ukraine's integration into the world economy [9]. Economic security can be viewed as the ability of an economy to achieve sustainable economic growth. Among other things, the economic security of a country depends on the international economic and political situation, relations with neighbors and membership in powerful international economic, political and military structures [10]. The generalized foreign experience in determining the determinants that determine the formation of economic security and analysis of the regulation of the processes of economic security of enterprises at the macro and micro levels, shows ways to improve the efficiency of the economic security of Ukraine as a whole [11, 12]. The results of research on economic development of countries in the context of the global economy and, in particular, the developed economies of the world and the EU and developing countries contribute to generalizing the effects of globalization on the world economy [13].

The only source of the formation of socio-economic security is its relationship with the external and internal environment of the functioning of the state at the national level and the enterprise at the local level, as well as with the degree of protection from dangers and threats of an economic nature. We believe that the definition of "economic security" solely from the point of view of forming a response to external threats is somewhat utilitarian and does not reflect the entire set of cause-and-effect relationships and components embodied in economic security from the point of view of its social aspects. That is why we propose to consider economic security in its dialectical relationship with the development of the enterprise and its balance in the temporary space of economic life.

With the development of the country, the issues of strengthening the economic security of the state and society are becoming increasingly relevant, as a result of which there is a need to study the determinants of the formation of national security, taking into account its most important component - the social one. Consequently, the determinants of socio-economic security are a set of processes of subjects and objects involved in ensuring security, interacting and connected in time and space by certain ways of socio-economic interaction, determined by the socio-economic status, goals and functions of security subjects [14].

The economic basis as a set of production relations of society, due to a certain level of development of material productive forces, determines its social structure. Indeed, in matters of ensuring the quality of life of society at different stages of its development, the main attention was paid to the social component of security. Anti-crisis management in the context of structural changes in the economy and globalization processes is the main tool for ensuring socio-economic security and focuses on minimizing or eliminating risks and threats through the use of modern methods and techniques, as well as modern management capabilities that allow de-

veloping the priority activities of a socially and economically promising business. In general, the socio-economic security component of national security is determined by effective operation of life support systems on their territories, production of necessary material goods, positive demographic changes, provision and restoration of all conditions necessary, first of all, for the activities of rural population, careful attitude to resources, and progress in the field of production, innovation and information. This set of security elements is also systemic, requiring the same systemic impact. Along with the development of measures to strengthen economic security as a component of national security at the macro level, economic security management at the level of economic entities plays a significant role.

The study allowed to supplement the theoretical ideas about the content of the category "socio-economic security", which until now was considered solely as a state of counteracting risks and threats and achieving competitive advantages in an unstable environment and identify features of socio-economic security. The structural transformation of the national economy ensures its adaptation to the global economic environment in order to meet social needs and ensure socio-economic growth. Diagnosis of the determinants of structural transformations of the economy by its main types indicates the presence of significant imbalances. This poses a threat to its sustainable development. In order to optimize and increase the degree of reliability of national economic security, it is necessary to pursue an active structural policy involving the potential of all state institutions. Structural policy should be based on a detailed analysis of the impact of basic market and social institutions on the structure of the domestic economy.

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